

DEVELOPMENT OF PEDESTRIAN PASSAGES IN THE TERRITORIES OF OUR REPUBLIC

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Abstract: In the article, pedestrian crossings in our republic, sidewalks that meet modern European requirements, various facilities for pedestrians, current and previous pedestrian crossings, pedestrian crossings in rural and urban areas. the difference between them is revealed. Pedestrians should move along sidewalks, footpaths, bicycle paths, and if they are not available, along the side of the road. Pedestrians carrying or carrying large objects, as well as people in non-motorized wheelchairs, may move from the edge of the carriageway if their movement on the sidewalk or shoulder would cause harm to other pedestrians. In the absence of sidewalks, footpaths, cycle paths or shoulders, and in the absence of the possibility of movement along them, pedestrians can move along the cycle path or walk in a row on the edge of the carriageway (with a dividing line). on the roads - on the outer edge of the carriageway)

Key words: Engine, road shoulder, bicycle, roadside

Pedestrians should walk along the edge of the carriageway in front of the movement of vehicles. People who drive wheelchairs without an engine, ride motorcycles, mopeds, bicycles must follow the instructions of vehicles in these cases.

It is recommended for pedestrians to carry objects with reflective elements when crossing the road and when moving on the shoulder or at the edge of the

carriageway at night or in low-visibility conditions, and outside of populated areas, pedestrians should carry objects with reflective elements, and drivers of vehicles should carry these objects. must ensure appearance.

The movement of organized columns of pedestrians on the carriageway is allowed only on the right side of vehicles in the direction of movement of no more than four people in a row. There should be red flags in front and behind the column on the left, escorts with lights on in the dark and in low-visibility streets: in front - white, behind - red.

Pedestrians must cross the road at pedestrian crossings, including underground and overpasses, in the absence of them - pedestrians at intersections along roads or shoulder lines.

In places where traffic is regulated, pedestrians must control the signals of the traffic controller or pedestrian traffic lights, and in its absence - the traffic lights.

It is allowed to wait for public transport vehicles and taxis only on the platforms raised above the carriageway, in their absence - on the sidewalk or on the shoulder. Route vehicles that are not equipped with raised landings are allowed to take off only after parking. After landing, it is necessary to clean the carriageway without delay.

Pedestrians must comply with the requirements of clauses 4.4-4.7 of the Pedestrian Rules when walking along the carriageway to or from the place where the route vehicle has stopped.

In the city of Andijan, special measures are taken to ensure traffic safety and to prevent road traffic accidents involving citizens, pedestrians, and children. In this city, the sidewalks are lit up after dark. This increases the attention of vehicle drivers at night and encourages them to be alert. More than 10,000 road traffic accidents occurred in our country in 2021, in which more than 9,000 people were injured. The saddest thing is that about 2,500 people died.

According to the analysis, 25 percent of road accidents are caused by poor road conditions and poor infrastructure. For example, the roads between Pop and Toraqorgon, Zharkorgon and Denov, Samarkand and Guzor, on the section of the A-373 road that passes through Yozhiovon district, dozens of people die every year. is dying. Unfortunately, such dangerous streets exist in every region, every district and city. The most effective way to manage the traffic flow is digitization. But it was shown that the works in this regard are not enough.

In particular, there are only 111 out of 602 intersections in the city of Tashkent with digital control. Other cities do not have such a system. An organized group of pedestrians is allowed to walk on the right side of the road, not more than four people in a row, only in the direction of movement of vehicles.

In the streets of the city of Namangan, a suspended pedestrian crossing has appeared. UzA reports about this. Do not rush to conclude that this must be a bridge or something similar. This lane is a "zebra" line drawn on the asphalt on city streets, in the language of drivers or traffic safety officers.

The President's attention to the introduction of innovative ideas and projects in all areas encouraged me to research this idea and I found what I was looking for, - says the head of the traffic control department of the Regional Department of Internal Affairs. senior lieutenant Elmurod Komilov - The project, initially presented on paper, was approved by the management, and it is recommended to implement it in one or two places as a test. The essence of this innovative idea is that the pedestrian crossing seems to be suspended in the eyes of the car driver coming from afar, and the driver increases alertness and reduces speed, as a result, the possibility of pedestrians crossing the road increases.

This effect is achieved by dropping the "zebra" on the asphalt in 3D format. The appearance of lines rising from the ground is created using shadows. For this, in addition to the usual white paint, two different companies of black and gray paint are required. The first two such pedestrian crossings were implemented in Oromgoh and Nodim Namangani streets of Namangan city. Komilov.-That is, if lines and shadows are treated with thermoplastic materials, they will be clearly visible even at night. Currently, 8 unregulated crossings of the city will have such crossings. In total, more than 40 such corridors will be gradually introduced new technology.

The conclusion is that pedestrian crossings play a very important role for mankind. Every province and district of our republic now has pedestrian crossings and they are being modernized. Everyone is working together to reduce traffic accidents so that people don't have to suffer. Not lagging behind in Europe, new ideas are being supported in our republic.

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